

Daring metabolic designs for enhanced plant carbon fixation[☆]

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Rubisco
Calvin cycle
Metabolic engineering
Synthetic biology
Photorespiration
Carboxylation
Formate assimilation

ABSTRACT

Increasing agricultural productivity is one of the major challenges our society faces. While multiple strategies to enhance plant carbon fixation have been suggested, and partially implemented, most of them are restricted to relatively simple modifications of endogenous metabolism, i.e., “low hanging fruit”. Here, I portray the next generation of metabolic solutions to increase carbon fixation rate and yield. These strategies involve major rewiring of central metabolism, including dividing Rubisco’s catalysis between several enzymes, replacing Rubisco with a different carboxylating enzyme, substituting the Calvin Cycle with alternative carbon fixation pathways, and engineering photorespiration bypass routes that do not release carbon. While the barriers for implementing these elaborated metabolic architectures are quite significant, if we truly want to revolutionize carbon fixation, only daring engineering efforts will lead the way.

1. Introduction

Global crop production needs to double by 2050 to meet the demands of a growing population. To achieve this goal, agricultural yield needs to increase by 2.4% per year, almost double the average annual yield increase in the past 40 years [1]. As the efficiency with which plants intercept light and the partitioning of biomass into harvested parts are close to their theoretical maxima, major improvements in plant productivity could mainly arise from increasing the efficiency by which solar energy is converted into biomass [2–4]. Averaged throughout the growing season, this efficiency is limited to a few percent, in spite of a theoretical maximum of ~12% [2–4]. Multiple factors, related to several key processes, were shown to limit the efficiency by which light is used to generate biomass; accordingly, numerous strategies for enhancing plant productivity have been proposed, and, at least some, have been tested *in vivo*. These strategies can be roughly divided into four categories, depending on the physiological process they are trying to optimize [3–11]: light reactions, CO₂ diffusion and concentration, activity of Rubisco, and regeneration of ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate (RuBP). Table 1 summarizes these approaches and provides references to representative studies and recent reviews that exemplify and discuss them.

This perspective aims to put forward (mostly) unconventional ideas to rewire carbon fixation metabolism for increased photosynthetic efficiency. As most current efforts center around “low hanging fruit”, i.e., minimal engineering interventions that maximize short-term gains, I decided to focus on long-term prospects to revolutionize carbon fixation

using both enzyme and metabolic engineering [12], as summarized schematically in Fig. 1. First, I discuss the distribution of Rubisco’s catalytic steps across several consecutive enzymes. This is followed by a suggestion to replace Rubisco with a different carboxylating enzyme while maintaining the Calvin Cycle largely intact. Then, I analyze the possibility of substituting the entire Calvin Cycle with alternative carbon fixation pathways. A special emphasis is given to synthetic carbon fixation pathways that rely on carbon reduction to formate, followed by formate assimilation. Finally, replacement of the CO₂-releasing photorespiration pathways with carbon-neutral or carbon-positive bypass routes is presented and analyzed.

Throughout the discussion, it is important to remember that besides directly enhancing plant productivity, increased carbon fixation efficiency holds more benefits for plant growth. First, Rubisco accounts for 30–50% of the total soluble proteins in the leaves of C3 plant, and holds 10–30% of the total nitrogen [7]. Increasing carbon fixation rate would enable a reduction in Rubisco levels, and therefore higher efficiency of nitrogen use, potentially alleviating a major growth constraint [4,7,13]. Similarly, establishing a higher carbon fixation rate could permit photosynthesis to operate under a lower chloroplastic concentration of inorganic carbon, thus enabling the plant to close its stomata when necessary and maintain higher efficiency of water use [4,7].

2. Dividing Rubisco’s reaction between multiple enzymes

The maximal rate of Rubisco is an order of magnitude lower than the average of central metabolism enzymes [14]. Its lack of specificity

[☆] This article is part of a special issue entitled “Synthetic biology meets plant metabolism”, published in the journal Plant Science 273, 2018.

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Table 1

Summary of previously suggested means to increase the efficiency by which light is used to generate biomass, as divided into four main categories.

	Ref.
Light reactions	
Engineer or use naturally occurring pigments to expand the photosynthetically active radiation spectrum to the infrared range	[89–91]
Reduce antenna size, especially in the upper canopy leaves, which trap too much light; thus saving cellular resources and enabling more light to reach the lower leaves	[91–93]
Re-wire the two photosystems to avoid competition on available light and split electron flow to enable each photosystem to work “independently” of the other	[3]
Optimize components of the electron transport chain and downstream acceptors (e.g., <i>b₆f</i> complex, NAD-kinase)	[94–96]
Accelerate adaptation of photosynthesis to fast shifting light intensities	[97–99]
Redistribute and rearrange crop canopy	[100–102]
CO₂ diffusion and concentration	
Engineer C4 cycle in C3 plants	[103–105]
Engineer CAM into C3 crops	[106,107]
Increase CO ₂ conductance by overexpression of aquaporins	[108–110]
Express bicarbonate transporters (e.g., cyanobacterial) in chloroplast envelop to increase chloroplastic CO ₂ concentration and match it to the leaf intracellular level	[111–113]
Establish cyanobacterial carboxysomes, together with other components of CCM (e.g., CO ₂ pumps that hydrate it to bicarbonate), to accumulate inorganic carbon in the chloroplast and saturate Rubisco with CO ₂	[6,113,114]
Express cyanobacterial IctB, which was shown to enhance CO ₂ assimilation in multiple crops (mechanism not clear)	[115–117]
Rubisco's carbon fixation activity	
Rational design or metabolic selection for improved kinetic parameters: enhancing carboxylation rate, lowering oxygenation rate, increasing specificity towards CO ₂	[118–120]
Replace endogenous Rubisco with variants with more suitable parameters (e.g., having higher <i>k_{cat}</i> , even at the expense of lower specificity)	[121–123]
Engineer Rubisco for poorer binding of its inhibitors (e.g., D-xylulose-1,5-bisphosphate)	[124,125]
Overexpress and/or increase the thermal stability of Rubisco activase	[126–128]
Regeneration of RuBP	
Introduce a naturally occurring, more efficient photorespiration route (still release CO ₂)	[35,70,72]
Engineer a photorespiration bypass that does not release CO ₂	[3,129]
Modulate enzyme levels within the Calvin Cycle and photorespiration (e.g., overexpression of sedoheptulose 1,7-bisphosphatase)	[130–132]
Replace the Calvin Cycle with a natural or synthetic route	[22,32,34]

Fig. 1. Schematic summary of the main strategies for increasing carbon fixation rate and yield as discussed in the manuscript.

towards CO₂ (see below section on oxygenation and photorespiration) further substantially reduces its effective carboxylation efficiency. Efforts to improve Rubisco's kinetic parameters resulted in marginal success at best [15], mainly due to the inherent tradeoff between the enzyme's rate and specificity [16]. Instead of trying to pursue small improvements in the activity of an enzyme that was under immense selective pressure for eons, we should consider replacing it with other enzymes that together take over its catalytic activity. An advantage of this approach is that it keeps the Calvin Cycle largely intact, thus

minimizing further disruption of the plant physiology. Rubisco's reaction involves four consecutive steps: enolization, CO₂/O₂ addition, hydration, and cleavage (Fig. 2A) [17,18]. These reaction steps could potentially be catalyzed by three enzymes, each operating via a well-established mechanism (Fig. 2B–D). The first would be an isomerase, transferring the carbonyl group from the second to the third carbon (Fig. 2B). This reaction is very similar to the one catalyzed by 6-phosphate-3-hexuloisomerase (EC 5.3.1.27) of the ribulose monophosphate (RuMP) cycle [19]. The second reaction is a carboxylation (Fig. 2C) that

(A) Rubisco's enzymatic mechanism

Fig. 2. Dividing Rubisco's catalysis between several enzymes. (A) Mechanism of Rubisco catalysis [17,18]. (B–D) Proposed mechanisms for three enzymes that could replace Rubisco. RuBP corresponds to ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate.

could be catalyzed by a biotin-dependent enzyme, which does not suffer from the problem of oxygenation. The location of the carbonyl group – on the third carbon – is ideal to support the required CO₂ addition reaction (Fig. 2C). Lastly, a third enzyme would catalyze a hydration-cleavage reaction, as shown in Fig. 2D, with a mechanism matching that of the enzyme oxaloacetase (EC 3.7.1.1) [20]. This set of enzymes, once evolved and optimized, could break the kinetic constraints imposed by Rubisco's mechanism, enabling unhindered improvement of catalytic rates. The extra ATP cost associated with the biotin dependent carboxylation is tolerable considering the complete suppression of oxygenation and photorespiration, and potentially improved kinetics that would substantially lower the protein burden associated with Rubisco biosynthesis. Moreover, biotin-dependent carboxylases accept bicarbonate instead of CO₂. As the concentration of bicarbonate in the alkaline stroma is orders of magnitude higher than that of CO₂, the availability of inorganic carbon is not expected to limit photosynthetic rate.

3. Substituting Rubisco with an alternative carboxylation reaction

It is conceivable to replace Rubisco with another carboxylase while keeping the basic operation of the Calvin Cycle mostly unhindered. 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase (6PGDH) presents such an opportunity. 6PGDH is a reversible reductive carboxylase (oxidative decarboxylase) operating at $\Delta_r G^m \sim +6$ kJ/mol (Gibbs energy change at $7 < \text{pH} < 8$, ionic strength of 0.25M, and assuming reactant concentrations of 1 mM [21]). Reductive carboxylases, which also include

the malic enzyme and isocitrate dehydrogenase, couple the favorable reduction of a carbonyl group to an unfavorable carboxylation [22]. A recent review has compared the kinetics of different carboxylase enzymes, revealing that the best reductive carboxylases have k_{cat} values higher than 100 s^{-1} , almost two orders of magnitude higher than that of Rubisco [23]. However, their maximal affinity towards CO₂ is 1 mM, almost two orders of magnitude worse than that of Rubisco. Together, k_{cat}/K_M values of these reductive carboxylases can be as high as that of Rubisco [23]. While the kinetics of 6PGDH in the reductive direction is mostly unexplored, it is plausible to assume that some of its variants – perhaps not plant ones but rather prokaryotic – have similar kinetics, making its rate comparable to that of Rubisco, without the problem of oxygenation. It is worth noting that if coupled to a carbon concentrating mechanism, 6PGDH kinetics would become even more favorable.

As a carboxylation substrate, 6PGDH accepts ribulose 5-phosphate (Ru5P), the direct precursor of ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate (RuBP), Rubisco's substrate. Hence, both carboxylation reactions share almost identical substrates. However, the products of the reactions are very different, leading to the question of how 6-phosphogluconate (6PG) – the product of 6PGDH carboxylation – is going to be recycled back into the Calvin Cycle. Several options can be envisioned. Reducing 6PG to glucose 6-phosphate – which is then isomerized to fructose 6-phosphate – would be the most straightforward approach (Fig. 3A). However, this is thermodynamically infeasible, unless the carboxyl group is activated – for example, as a phosphoanhydride group. Therefore, to enable the operation of this cycle it is vital to establish glucose 6-phosphate

Fig. 3. Replacing Rubisco with 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase. 6-phosphogluconate could be recycled back into the Calvin Cycle in four different ways. Novel reactions are shown in purple. As all pathway variants overlap with the Calvin Cycle, triose phosphate can be exported and directed to sucrose biosynthesis and fructose 6-phosphate can be directed to chloroplastic starch biosynthesis. As glucose 6-phosphate is an intermediate of the pathway variant shown in (A), it can be directly used for the biosynthesis of starch. (A) Enzymes: (1) 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase; (2) 6-phosphogluconate 1-kinase; (3) glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase (phosphorylating); (4) glucose 6-phosphate isomerase. (B) Enzymes: (1) 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase; (2) 6-phosphogluconate 2-dehydrogenase; (3) 2-keto-6-phosphogluconate aldolase; (4) hydroxypyruvate reductase; (5) glycerate 3-kinase. (C) Enzymes: (1) 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase; (2) 6-phosphogluconate 2-dehydrogenase; (3) 2-keto-6-phosphogluconate aldolase; (4) hydroxypyruvate reductase; (5) glycerate 3-kinase. (D) Enzymes: (1) 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase; (2) 6-phosphogluconate 5-dehydrogenase; (3) 5-keto-6-phosphogluconate aldolase; (4) tartronate semialdehyde reductase; (5) glycerate 3-kinase.

dehydrogenase (phosphorylating) and 6PG-1-kinase activities, which could potentially be evolved from glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (phosphorylating) and 3-phosphoglycerate kinase, respectively. Supporting this possibility, human glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase was already shown to accept glucose [24]. As the activity of the glucose 6-phosphate shunt [25] directly counteracts the reductive assimilation of 6 PG, it would probably have to be deleted (e.g., knocking out glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase, ZWF). Yet, this shunt is predicted to play an important role in stabilizing the activity of the Calvin Cycle [25] and its deletion might result in deleterious effects.

Conversely, 6 PG can be reassimilated using only existing enzymes (Fig. 3B): the enzymes of the Entner–Doudoroff pathway – 6-phosphogluconate dehydratase and 2-keto-3-deoxy-6-phosphogluconate aldolase – can metabolize 6 PG to GAP and pyruvate. Pyruvate can then be reassimilated into the Calvin Cycle via gluconeogenesis. However, chloroplasts do not contain the enzymes of lower glycolysis – phosphoglycerate mutase and enolase [26–28] – and their introduction to

this organelle could result in a major disruption of endogenous metabolism.

Two other pathways could recycle 6 PG with little overlap with endogenous metabolism. In these pathways (Fig. 3C,D), a hydroxyl group of 6 PG is oxidized to give a carbonyl, followed by an aldolase reaction that produces a triose phosphate and glycerate, which can be directly fed into the Calvin Cycle. The 2-keto-6-phosphogluconate pathway (Fig. 3C) might be more approachable, as 6-phosphogluconate 2-dehydrogenase actually exists (EC 1.1.1.43), while 6-phosphogluconate 5-dehydrogenase (Fig. 3D) needs to be engineered. The aldol cleavage of 2-keto-6-phosphogluconate (Fig. 3C) and 5-keto-6-phosphogluconate (Fig. 3D) requires enzyme engineering, but enzymes that catalyze similar reactions are available. For example, 2-dehydro-3-deoxyglucuronate aldolase (EC 4.1.2.20) catalyzes the cleavage of this metabolite to pyruvate and tartronate semialdehyde [29], demonstrating an aldolase reaction that generate this later glycerate-precursor.

Box 1

Analysis and comparison of synthetic metabolic pathways.

The design of novel pathways – supporting carbon fixation, alternative photorespiration, or any other metabolic task – requires an intricate analysis framework to compare the different candidate routes. Multiple physiochemical parameters should be considered in such an analysis. While these criteria can change from one study to another, there are several global parameters that deserve elaboration:

1. *Resource consumption.* Pathways should not waste cellular resources, especially ATP, if not strictly needed to support activity. Minimization of ATP utilization will ensure high growth yield when cell energetics is constrained, e.g., under low light intensities. Yet, ATP-utilization should be high enough as to make the pathway thermodynamically feasible as discussed below. Another important aspect is a balanced consumption of the cellular resources. Specifically, the photosynthetic production of ATP and NADPH occur at a particular stoichiometry which is not completely fixed but still restricted to a limited range [133–135]. Ideally, pathways which utilize these resources should consume them in a similar stoichiometry, avoiding imbalances that could disrupt cellular activity. The synthetic carbon fixation pathways put forward in this manuscript, commonly being more ATP-efficient than the Calvin Cycle, do not adhere to 3 ATP: 2 NADPH stoichiometry of the Calvin Cycle and could potentially lead to accumulation of ATP. However, as ATP surplus is easier to export or dissipate than a surplus of reducing power, this imbalance is not expected to represent a major difficulty.

2. *Thermodynamics.* All pathway reactions should be thermodynamically feasible under physiological conditions – pH 7–8, ionic strength of 0.25 mM, metabolite concentrations between 1 μ M to 10 mM [30,136,137] – both individually and as a part of the overall pathway. The latter issue is especially important since a sequence of several reactions – feasible by themselves – could together lead to an unfeasible pathway as the energetic barriers of the reactions accumulate. A pathway should not only be thermodynamically feasible but should also be supported by sufficiently high thermodynamic driving force; that is, in order operate at high rate and low protein burden, each of the pathway reactions should preferably dissipate at least 2–3 kJ/mol [136].

3. *Kinetics.* All pathway enzymes should preferably operate with high k_{cat} and low K_M . As different enzymatic mechanisms vary greatly in the maximal rates they can support [14], pathways that depend only on enzyme classes that are known to support high rates are preferable over those that include enzymatic mechanisms that are characterized by poor kinetics.

4. *Metabolites.* The metabolic intermediates of the pathway should be as benign as possible, i.e., not too reactive or toxic and not too hydrophobic as to leak out from the organelle or the cell [138]. For example, concentrations of reactive aldehydes should be kept low. Furthermore, metabolites that incorporate cofactors of low abundance should be kept at low concentration or completely avoided. For example, CoA concentration in the chloroplast is very low, 1–5 μ M [139]. Hence, pathways that include many CoA-acetylated species might require challenging regulation to avoid the depletion of this central cofactor.

5. *Connectivity.* Autocatalytic cycles – that is, metabolic cycles whose product is an intermediate of the pathway – are generally preferable, as they can sustain continuous flux via the pathway even if its intermediates are drained for other metabolic purposes. However, these metabolic designs must meet specific conditions to support stable fluxes. For example, the affinity of enzymes that consume the pathway intermediates – i.e., pooling them out of the of autocatalytic cycles – must be limited to prevent metabolite depletion [140]. Also, pathway overlap with endogenous metabolism should be minimized. If such overlap does exist it is important that no ‘clash’ between the fluxes occur in terms of direction and regulation. As much as possible, metabolic pathways that are separated in the endogenous metabolic network should not be connected via the synthetic pathway. For example, chloroplastic separation of upper and lower glycolysis should most likely be maintained. It is further important to connect the pathway output with downstream metabolism in an efficient manner; for carbon fixation this mostly means the direct conversion of the product into triose phosphate and glucose 6-phosphate, the precursors for sucrose and starch biosynthesis.

6. *Regulation.* While not a physiochemical parameter *per se*, regulation is a key factor that affects pathway activity. It is also the most difficult factor to control and engineer. Natural pathways ensure that the metabolic flux is adjusted simultaneously at several points in response to changes in inputs and outputs. As engineering such a response in a synthetic pathway is very challenging, it is important to try and minimize the need for such control points. For example, limiting the number of irreversible enzymes might be useful, as the activity of these usually require special regulation to avoid flux imbalances and accumulation of intermediates.

4. Synthetic carbon fixation pathways

Six pathways are known to support carbon fixation in autotrophic organisms. Of these, the Calvin Cycle can be considered as the least efficient one. In all other pathways, ATP is invested only to energize unfavorable reactions that are essential for carbon fixation: carboxylation and carboxyl reduction [30]. Moreover, many of the other pathways couple these unfavorable reactions to exergonic reactions other than ATP hydrolysis, thus reducing ATP consumption. On the other hand, the Calvin Cycle is the only carbon fixation pathway that hydrolyzes ATP for purposes other than activating unfavorable reactions. Specifically, the ATP consumed by phosphoribulokinase does not help to overcome any thermodynamic barrier [30]. While this phosphorylation reaction plays a role in ensuring that all pathway intermediates are phosphorylated and further enables two irreversible steps – fructose 1,6-bisphosphatase and sedoheptulose 1,7-bisphosphatase – that generate extra thermodynamic push and enable better flux control, these are not strictly necessary for pathway activity. Biochemically, it would have been possible to operate the cycle with non-phosphorylated

sugars and without the irreversible bisphosphatases, achieving the same metabolic goal with a lower ATP cost. The extra ATP consumption of the Calvin Cycle reduces the efficiency of the pathway and decreases the biomass yield it can support (under energy-limited conditions). As such, the Calvin Cycle suffers from two major inefficiencies, the first related to the poor kinetics of its carboxylating enzyme and the second to its wasteful use of cellular resources.

This leads to the question of whether the Calvin Cycle can be replaced with another pathway that could support higher carbon fixation rate and efficiency. Out of the known natural pathways, only two are oxygen-tolerant enough to potentially operate within the oxygen-rich chloroplast: the 3-hydroxypropionate bicycle and the 3-hydroxypropionate-4-hydroxybutyrate cycle [22,31]. Both pathways are based on efficient biotin-dependent carboxylations [23], directly tapping into the extended reservoir of plastidic bicarbonate. However, both pathways are rather complex, in terms of enzymatic steps and overlap with central metabolism. For example, both pathways interact with fatty-acid biosynthesis (malonyl-CoA metabolism), which could distort this essential chloroplastic process.

Fig. 4. A MOG pathway. A synthetic carbon fixation pathway based on PEP carboxylase – the most efficient carboxylating enzyme [32]. Reaction 5 exchanges a carboxyl group between oxaloacetate and acetyl-CoA. Reaction 7 exchanges an amine group between α -alanine and malonate semialdehyde. Glyoxylate, the pathway product, can be metabolized to tartronate semialdehyde, glycerate, and glycerate 3-phosphate. Glycerate 3-phosphate can be further converted, via gluconeogenesis, to triose phosphate and glucose 6-phosphate, which the cell can use for sucrose and starch biosynthesis. Enzymes: (1) PEP carboxylase; (2) malate dehydrogenase; (3) maly-CoA synthetase; (4) maly-CoA lyase; (5) methylmalonyl-CoA carboxyltransferase; (6) malonate-semialdehyde dehydrogenase (acetylating); (7) beta-alanine—pyruvate transaminase; (8) alanine 2,3-aminomutase; (9) PEP synthase.

As an alternative, synthetic pathways can be designed to offer tailored metabolic solutions for carbon fixation. Two general approaches can be used towards this goal: (i) considering only existing enzymes, potentially from different sources, which are combined together in a “mix-and-match” approach to offer a novel carbon fixation route [32];

Fig. 5. The CETCH cycle. An *in vitro* reconstructed synthetic carbon fixation pathway, based on reductive carboxylation [34]. Glyoxylate, the pathway product, can be metabolized to tartronate semialdehyde, glycerate, and glycerate 3-phosphate. Glycerate 3-phosphate can be further converted, via gluconeogenesis, to triose phosphate and glucose 6-phosphate, which the cell can use for sucrose and starch biosynthesis. Enzymes: (1) crotonyl-CoA carboxylase/reductase; (2) ethylmalonyl-CoA epimerase & mutase; (3) methylsuccinyl-CoA oxidase; (4) methylmalyl-CoA dehydratase; (5) methylmalyl-CoA lyase; (6) propionyl-CoA oxidase; (7) crotonyl-CoA carboxylase/reductase; (8) methylmalonyl-CoA epimerase & mutase; (9) succinate semialdehyde dehydrogenase (acetylating); (10) 4-hydroxybutyrate dehydrogenase; (11) 4-hydroxybutyryl-CoA synthetase; (12) 4-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydratase.

Fig. 6. A short synthetic carbon fixation pathway based on novel reactions. The non-natural reactions, marked in purple, include a biotin-dependent carboxylase operating on 3-hydroxypropionyl-CoA (reaction 4) which is followed by mutase/epimerase enzyme(s) generating maly-CoA (reaction 5). Glyoxylate, the pathway product, can be metabolized to tartronate semialdehyde, glycerate, and glycerate 3-phosphate. Glycerate 3-phosphate can be further converted, via gluconeogenesis, to triose phosphate and glucose 6-phosphate, which the cell can use for sucrose and starch biosynthesis. Enzymes: (1) acetyl-CoA carboxylase; (2) malonyl-CoA reductase; (3) 3-hydroxypropionyl-CoA synthetase; (4) 3-hydroxypropionyl-CoA carboxylase; (5) 3-hydroxymethylmalonyl-CoA epimerase & mutase; (6) maly-CoA lyase.

(ii) employing enzyme engineering techniques to evolve novel catalytic capabilities, which can be combined with existing enzymes to enable highly efficient carbon assimilation [12]. While the first approach is more straightforward, the second could lead to the development of highly optimized metabolic structures, the efficiency of which cannot be reached using only known enzymatic components [12]. Regardless of the approach taken, candidate synthetic pathways should be analyzed according to multiple physiochemical parameters in order to identify those that are most suitable to support *in vivo* carbon fixation. The central parameters to consider are summarized in Box 1.

Synthetic carbon fixation pathways have yet to be implemented in

Fig. 7. The reductive glycine pathway, supporting formate assimilation [38,39]. ‘H’ corresponds to the H protein of the glycine cleavage system. THF moiety is shown in brown and lipoic acid in green. 3-phosphoglycerate, the pathway product, can be metabolized, via gluconeogenesis, to triose phosphate and glucose 6-phosphate, which the cell can use for sucrose and starch biosynthesis. Enzymes: (1) CO₂ reductase (formate dehydrogenase); (2) formate-THF ligase; (3) 5-formyltetrahydrofolate cycloligase & 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase; (4) glycine dehydrogenase (decarboxylating); (5) aminomethyltransferase; (6) dihydroliipoamide dehydrogenase; (7) serine hydroxymethyltransferase; (8) serine aminotransferase; (9) hydroxypyruvate reductase; (10) glycerate 3-kinase.

living organisms. However, an *in silico* study has identified numerous candidate pathways that could potentially replace the Calvin Cycle [32]. Among these, one group of pathways, termed the MOG (Malonyl-CoA-Oxaloacetate-Glyoxylate) cycles, was estimated to be especially promising in terms of efficiency and rate. As exemplified by one variant, shown in Fig. 4, the MOG cycles utilize a single carboxylating enzyme: PEP carboxylase (acetyl-CoA conversion to malonyl-CoA

proceeds via a carboxyl-transferase enzyme [33]). PEP carboxylase is the best carboxylating enzyme in terms of k_{cat} and k_{cat}/K_M [23,32], and could thus provide an optimal *in vivo* entry point of inorganic carbon. Recently, a synthetic carbon fixation cycle was established *in vitro*, demonstrating, for the first time, that this central process can be supported by a non-natural metabolic structure [34]. The CETCH cycle, as shown in Fig. 5, utilizes reductive carboxylation to efficiently add CO₂ onto metabolic intermediates and was shown to support a higher carbon fixation rate than the Calvin Cycle [34]. However, both the MOG cycles and the CETCH cycle produce glyoxylate, the assimilation of which into central metabolism – via the bacterial glycerate pathway [35] – is rather inefficient as it involves a decarboxylation step. Moreover, these cycles are very long and highly complicated. While implementing these pathways in microbes might be possible, their integration into the plant metabolic network seems highly unlikely. If one considers also unnatural reactions, simpler, more direct pathways can be proposed. To give only one example, carboxylation of 3-hydroxypropionate – via a promiscuous a biotin-dependent carboxylase, e.g., [36] – followed by a mutase and epimerase reactions – as are normally operated on methylmalonyl-CoA [37] – would result in a very short pathway, shown in Fig. 6, which might be considerably easier to implement.

5. Carbon fixation via CO₂ reduction

Many efforts to improve carbon fixation have focused on re-designing, analyzing, and optimizing the activity of carboxylating enzymes. However, these can be, at least partially, replaced by CO₂ reducing enzymes, followed by condensation of the reduced C1 compound with a metabolic intermediate [23]. Reduction of CO₂ results in one of two compounds: CO or formate. As the redox potential associated with CO is very low ($E^0 < -500$ mV [21]), the reduction of CO₂ to CO using cellular electron carriers is very challenging. Furthermore, since the assimilation of CO can proceed only via the highly oxygen sensitive acetyl-CoA synthase, this compound is of little interest in the context of plant metabolism. Formate, on the other hand, is associated with a less negative reduction potential ($E^0 \sim -420$ mV [21]), making its production from CO₂ an easier task. Furthermore, multiple formate assimilation pathways can be envisioned and tailored to fit the host organisms [38]. Therefore, an alternative carbon fixation strategy could be envisioned in which the low reduction potential of the chloroplastic electron carriers (e.g., ferredoxins) is used to reduce CO₂ to formate, which is then assimilated to central metabolism. As formate assimilation can be considerably more ATP-efficient than the Calvin Cycle, this approach could enhance biomass yield [23,39].

Reduction of CO₂ to formate can be catalyzed by formate dehydrogenase (FDH). Some metal-dependent variants of this enzyme were shown to support high CO₂-reduction activity [40]. For example, FDH from *Desulfovibrio desulfuricans* catalyzes CO₂ reduction with $k_{cat} \sim 50$ s⁻¹ and $K_M \sim 15$ μM, making this enzyme a much more efficient entry point for inorganic carbon than Rubisco [41]. However, this enzyme variant is highly oxygen sensitive. Other CO₂-reducing FDHs operate under fully aerobic conditions, e.g., FDH from *Rhodobacter capsulatus* [42] and from *Cupriavidus necator* [43]. The latter enzyme was shown to reduce CO₂ with $k_{cat} > 10$ s⁻¹. The most challenging aspect of establishing FDH activity within the chloroplast is that the enzyme is molybdenum-dependent. This means that molybdenum needs to be transported to the chloroplast and then embedded within the enzyme active site using a molybdenum cofactor (MoCo). Yet, the plant MoCo is not present in the chloroplast and is different than the bacterial variant that is required for FDH activity [44]. Hence, the entire biosynthesis pathway for the bacterial MoCo will have to be introduced into the chloroplast, together with an appropriate molybdenum transport system.

Once formate is generated from CO₂ reduction it needs to be assimilated. One promising formate assimilation route is the reductive

Fig. 8. The ribulose monophosphate (RuMP) pathway integrates with the endogenous Calvin Cycle. The RuMP pathway can support carbon fixation via reduction of CO₂ to formate and formaldehyde. Red arrows represent to the enzymes that need to be added to the Calvin Cycle to enable this metabolism. Formate reduction to formaldehyde (reaction 2), is likely to be catalyzed in two sequential reactions – the first activates formate and the second reduces the activated formate to formaldehyde [54]. Enzymes: (1) CO₂ reductase (formate dehydrogenase); (2) formaldehyde dehydrogenase system, i.e., formyl-CoA synthetase & formaldehyde dehydrogenase (acetylating); (3) 3-hexulose-6-phosphate synthase; (4) 6-phospho-3-hexuloisomerase.

glycine pathway, as shown in Fig. 7 [38,39,45]. The production of glycinate 3-phosphate via this pathway requires the investment of three ATP molecules instead of the eight needed by the Calvin Cycle. The pathway utilizes only enzymes that are known to operate in plant cells: attachment of formate to THF, followed by its reduction to methylene-THF (CH₂-THF) is supported by ubiquitous enzymes that exist in the chloroplast, cytosol and mitochondria [46]; the glycine cleavage system (GCV) and serine hydroxymethyltransferase operate in the mitochondria [47]; and conversion of serine to glycinate occurs in the peroxisome and cytosol [48]. Taken together, the reductive glycine pathway overlaps with the native photorespiration pathway, but re-wires it from being a carbon releasing process (see below) into a Calvin-Cycle-independent carbon fixation route. The GCV is known to be reversible both *in vitro* [49,50] and *in vivo* [51–53], and its overall thermodynamics ($\Delta_r G^{m'} \sim -5$ kJ/mol in the reductive direction, pH 7–8, I = 0.25 M [21]) indicates that its flux direction is determined by the concentrations of the reactants (THF, CH₂-THF, glycinate, CO₂, NH₃, NAD⁺, NADH). Yet, the GCV from plants was never demonstrated to work in the reductive direction, suggesting that a foreign, well-established reversible system might be necessary to support glycinate biosynthesis.

Another interesting approach involves formate reduction to formaldehyde, which is then assimilated via the RuMP pathway [19], as shown in Fig. 8. Reduction of formate, via a formyl-CoA intermediate, has been previously demonstrated using promiscuous acetyl-CoA

synthetase and acetaldehyde dehydrogenase [54]. 3-Hexulose-6-phosphate synthase (HPS) and 6-phospho-3-hexuloisomerase (PHI), the key enzymes of the RuMP pathway were already shown to be fully active when expressed in plant chloroplast, supporting the assimilation of exogenously supplied formaldehyde [55,56]. As the affinity of HPS to formaldehyde is very high (K_M as low as 59 μ M) and the enzyme operates at very high rate (k_{cat} as high as 97 s⁻¹) [19], the steady-state concentration of formaldehyde can remain very low, avoiding the toxicity effects associated with its accumulation. The main advantage of the RuMP pathway is that it is much more efficient in the utilization of cellular resources than the Calvin Cycle: production of a triose phosphate from CO₂ requires only 4 ATP molecules (assuming that formate activation with CoA requires a single ATP), which is less than half of the 9 ATP molecules hydrolyzed by the Calvin Cycle. Moreover, formaldehyde assimilation is metabolically contained within the Calvin Cycle, i.e., converting ribulose 5-phosphate to fructose 6-phosphate. This could minimize the disturbance to endogenous fluxes and reduce regulation complexity.

6. Photorespiration bypasses

In C3 plants Rubisco's oxygenation accounts for 20–30% of catalytic turnovers [57–62], producing large amount of 2-phosphoglycolate (2PG) that needs to be recycled into the Calvin Cycle in a process termed photorespiration. Photorespiration also plays a central role in

Fig. 12. Converting photorespiration into a carbon positive process by engineering CO₂ reduction to formate. Formate is then assimilated and reduced to enable glycine conversion to serine without releasing carbon. THF moiety is shown in brown. CH₂-THF corresponds to 5,10-methylene-THF. Enzymes: (1) phosphoglycolate phosphatase; (2) glycolate oxidase; (3) glycine aminotransferase; (4) serine hydroxymethyltransferase; (5) serine aminotransferase; (6) hydroxypyruvate reductase; (7) glycerate 3-kinase; (8) CO₂ reductase (formate dehydrogenase); (9) formate-THF ligase; (10) 5-formyltetrahydrofolate cycloligase & 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase.

activity of the Calvin Cycle and Rubisco. Replacing photorespiration with a synthetic alternative could tackle one or more of these drawbacks.

Several CO₂-releasing photorespiration bypass routes – some shown in Fig. 9 – were previously suggested and at least partially implemented [35,70–72]. These were analyzed in multiple studies and reviews [5,73–76], and hence will not be discussed in detail here. Yet, it should be noted that the mechanism behind the beneficial effect of the most studied bypass, the glycerate pathway, remains somewhat vague. In this pathway, two glyoxylate molecules are directly condensed into tartronate semialdehyde (and CO₂) which is subsequently reduced to glycerate, all within the chloroplast [35,72] (Fig. 9). However, it was found that the overexpression of glycolate dehydrogenase by itself – shown to increase glyoxylate content in chloroplasts – exerts a similar beneficial effect on photosynthetic productivity [35,72,77]. It is therefore difficult to decipher whether the enhancement of carbon fixation by the chloroplastic glycerate pathway is truly related to the more efficient recycling of glycolate.

As CO₂ release is the main drawback of photorespiration, a metabolic bypass which would avoid this carbon loss could have a much more substantial effect on carbon fixation than the CO₂-releasing pathways. Fig. 10 shows a possible general structure of such alternative photorespiration routes. In these pathways, glycolate is first reduced to glycolaldehyde, via a glycolyl-phosphate or glycolyl-CoA intermediate. Glycolaldehyde then serves either as an acceptor (Fig. 10A) or a donor (Fig. 10B) for an aldol condensation with a phosphosugar intermediate of the Calvin Cycle, resulting in the production of a longer chain phosphosugar than can be reintegrated into the cycle. As glycolaldehyde inhibits the Calvin Cycle [78–80], and, being a small aldehyde, is quite reactive [81–83], it is important to use an aldolase that can accept

Fig. 13. Glyoxylate cleavage into two formate molecules enables carbon-neutral photorespiration. The pathway converts glycine to serine with no release of CO₂. Cleavage reaction is shown in purple. THF moiety is shown in brown. Reaction stoichiometry is shown in green. CH₂-THF corresponds to 5,10-methylene-THF. Enzymes: (1) phosphoglycolate phosphatase; (2) glycolate oxidase; (3) glycine aminotransferase; (4) serine hydroxymethyltransferase; (5) serine aminotransferase; (6) hydroxypyruvate reductase; (7) glycerate 3-kinase; (8) glyoxylate formate-lyase; (9) formate-THF ligase; (10) 5-formyltetrahydrofolate cycloligase & 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase.

it with high affinity, thus preventing its accumulation and keeping its concentration below 1 mM.

Recently, a similar metabolic structure was suggested as a photorespiration bypass, where 2 PG is reduced to 2-phosphoglycolaldehyde, which is then condensed with dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP) to give xylulose 1,5-bisphosphate. Xylulose 1,5-bisphosphate is integrated to the Calvin Cycle via its dephosphorylation to xylulose 5-phosphate [3]. However, direct reduction of 2 PG is not advisable as the concentration of this metabolite is probably very low, unlike the high levels of glycolate [84] that push forward its reduction both energetically and kinetically.

An even more daring approach would be to transform photorespiration from a carbon-releasing process into a carbon-fixing one. By using this tactic, the burden of assimilating inorganic carbon would be shared between Rubisco and the photorespiratory carboxylating enzyme. In the extreme case, Rubisco could be evolved to catalyze only the oxygenation reaction – at very high rate – where carbon fixation is performed only via photorespiration. A previously suggested carbon-fixing photorespiration bypass converts glyoxylate to pyruvate via one of the cycles of the 3-hydroxypropionate bicycle [85], as shown in Fig. 11. While this provides a very interesting approach, the length of this bypass makes it very challenging to implement. Moreover, the cycle's product, pyruvate, needs to be assimilated back into the Calvin Cycle. As discussed above, this involves introducing missing glycolytic enzymes to the chloroplast – phosphoglycerate mutase and enolase – which could result in a severe flux disruption.

Identifying promising carbon-neutral and carbon-positive photorespiration bypass routes should follow the general guidelines presented in Box 1. While this manuscript is not the place to perform such a comprehensive analysis, there are two interesting routes that are worth

a short discussion. First, CO₂ reduction to formate, followed by reduction to CH₂-THF and condensation with glycine to give serine, can transform photorespiration into a carbon-fixing process, as shown in Fig. 12. This pathway is similar to the reductive glycine pathway (Fig. 7), where the main difference is that the photorespiration bypass is not dependent on *de novo* glycine production via the glycine cleavage system and as such is easier to implement. Notably, assimilation of formate into serine, in line with the suggested flux of this pathway, was demonstrated before *in planta* [86,87]. A more speculative route is shown in Fig. 13, where glyoxylate is cleaved into two formate molecules ($\Delta_r G^m < -45 \text{ kJ/mol}$ [21]), which, upon activation and reduction to CH₂-THF, can replace glycine cleavage and make photorespiration a carbon-neutral process. Yet, while the oxidation of glyoxylate to formate (releasing CO₂) was suggested to support a similar alternative photorespiration [86,87], a non-oxidative cleavage of glyoxylate into two formate molecules was not reported. Although an enzymatic mechanism to support this reaction is challenging to identify, a previous report on the condensation of formate into glyoxylate in potato tubers – although thus far unverified by other groups – suggests that it might be possible [88].

7. Concluding remarks

The metabolic solutions suggested here are by no means easy to execute. In fact, as I elaborated for each approach separately, considerable barriers await the researcher who will try to implement them in plants. Yet, in the long-run, and as our enzyme and metabolic engineering capabilities improve, especially *in planta* [3], some of the proposed strategies might prove feasible and could completely transform the way plants perform carbon fixation, enhancing productivity in an unparalleled way. It is further important to emphasize that the metabolic architectures suggested here do not necessarily have to replace the endogenous pathways, but can rather, at least initially, operate in parallel, providing support to the natural processes. For example, carbon fixation via CO₂ reduction to formate can operate next to the Calvin Cycle, where formate is assimilated via the reductive glycine pathway or (followed by another reduction) the ribulose monophosphate cycle, both directly integrate into Calvin Cycle. While it is not clear yet which solution will show the greatest promise *in vivo*, the time is ripe to expand our horizons towards daring metabolic designs that could reshape the most central biochemical process and enable us to boldly tackle a prime challenge of our society.

Acknowledgements

The work was funded by the Max Planck Society, the European Commission FET Open grant FutureAgriculture (project number 686330), and by the German Ministry of Education and Research grant FormatPlant (part of BioEconomy 2030, Plant Breeding Research for the Bioeconomy). The author thanks Nico Claassens, Charlie Cotton, Tobias Erb, and Steffen Lindner for suggestions and critical reading of the manuscript.

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